

STRYCHNINE AND BRUCINE. PART II THE ALKALINE DEGRADATION OF BRUCINE.

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The basic fraction obtained by the alkaline degradation of brucine has been fractionated and picrates have been obtained from these fractions. Among the products a base (picrate, m. p. 142°) is common to strychnine and brucine and is also identical with the base A described by Clemo.

Oechner (*Ann. chim. phys.* 1882, v, 27, 507) investigated the action of potassium hydroxide on brucine (for details vide *Compt. rend.*, 1882, 99, 1077; *Bull. Soc. chim.*, 1881, 42, 100). Later Brend and Stöhr (*J. pr., Chem.*, 1890, ii, 42, 4161) by distilling brucine with soda lime obtained ammonia, methylamine, β -picoline, and β -ethylpyridine which they analysed as mercury salt. In the present work brucine has been distilled with potassium hydroxide and the basic fraction, isolated from the distillate, has been distilled in *vacuo* and then fractionated into six fractions of which the last is too small for investigation. The remaining five fractions have been converted into picrates.

Fraction I gives a picrate which after repeated crystallisation is obtained in shining bright yellow prisms, m. p. 143-44° (m. p. 145-48° as found by Clemo, *private communication*). It gives analytical values in agreement with C_7H_9N but the m. p. of the picrate does not correspond to the picrate of any of the lutidines. The b. p. is close to that of 2-ethyl-lutidine but the m. p. of the picrate of this base is not recorded in the literature.

Fraction II gives a mixture of picrates, m. p. *circa* 104.5°.

Fraction III gives a picrate which melts at 141-42° (m. p. 143-44° found by Clemo) and does not depress the m. p. of the picrate obtained from strychnine by fusion with potassium hydroxide (*vide* previous part). The m. p. of the picrate and the boiling point of the base corresponds to that of the picrate of 2-methyl-4-ethylpyridine and the free base but differs when directly compared (*vide* Part I).

Fraction IV mostly gives the picrate, m. p. 141-42° and gives no depression on admixture with the picrate of fraction III.

Fraction V distills at 50°/1.5 mm. and the picrate obtained from it melts at 172°. Its analysis agrees with $C_{11}H_{11}N$ or $C_{11}H_{13}N$.

The filtrates from different fractions yield crystalline bright yellow picrates of varying melting points. Judging from their general behaviour,

solubilities and smell, it can safely be assumed that they are pyridine derivatives.

In the present state of our knowledge brucine can be represented as dimethoxy derivative of strychnine having the formula (II) of the previous paper.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Fusion of Brucine with Caustic Potash (cf. Abstracts of Dissertations, Oxford, 1938, p. 173).—

Brucine (1 part), mixed with powdered potassium hydroxide (2 parts), was placed in a copper flask over a layer of potassium hydroxide (1 part), and the top covered with further amount (1 part) of the alkali. The flask was fitted with a condenser and a receiver cooled in ice. An oil with some water distilled over on gradual heating and the evolved gases were found to be strongly alkaline to litmus. The distillate was shaken with ether and the ethereal solution extracted with 10% dilute hydrochloric acid. The acid extract was made alkaline with sodium hydroxide and extracted with ether. The ethereal solution after washing with water and drying over solid potassium hydroxide furnished a brownish yellow oil as residue, yield 5%. On distillation in *vacuo* it was obtained as a light pale yellow liquid with a penetrating odour which deepened in colour on standing. It was next distilled at atmospheric pressure and collected in six fractions of which the last was very small in amount.

Fraction I (b. p. 145-50°/764 mm., 5 g.), in ether (50 c.c.) was precipitated with ethereal picric acid solution, and the bright yellow picrate separated in prisms and plates. It was well washed with ether (8 g.), m. p. 124-25°. A further quantity (3.5 g., m. p. 124-25°) was obtained from the filtrate. The combined fractions were crystallised from methyl alcohol several times. It was finally obtained in glistening bright yellow prisms, m. p. 143-44° (m. p. 145-48° as found by Clemo). It is soluble in acetone, alcohol, warm water, difficultly in ethyl acetate, benzene and chloroform and is insoluble in petroleum ether. After drying at 100° in *vacuo* it suffered no loss in weight. [Found: C, 45.9, 45.8; H, 3.5, 3.1; N, 16.7, 17.0. $C_6H_2N \cdot C_6H_2(NO_2)_3(OH)$ requires C, 46.4; H, 3.6; N, 16.7 per cent].

Fraction II (b.p. 155-65°/764 mm., 0.65 g.) was similarly converted into a bright yellow picrate which on recrystallisation from methyl alcohol melted at 104.5° with gradual softening. It appears to be a mixture of fraction I and fraction III.

Fraction III (b.p. 170-175°/764 mm., 2.7 g.) gave a bright yellow picrate (4.9 g.), m. p. *circa* 104° and the orange filtrate and washings showed

a green fluorescence. On crystallising several times from methyl alcohol it melted at 135-36°. It gives no appreciable depression with the picrate of the fraction IV (m.p. 141-42°) but when mixed with the picrate of fraction I it melted at 105-12°.

Fraction IV (b.p. 180°/764 mm., 3·8 g.) was dissolved in ether and on adding ethereal solution of picric acid bright yellow prisms were obtained after washing with ether (5 g.). The picrate melted at 120-24° but on crystallising four times from methyl alcohol it was obtained in long shining lemon-yellow plates and leaflets, m. p. 141-42° and three subsequent crystallisations did not raise the m. p. further. It showed depression when admixed with the picrate of the above obtained from strychnine (*vide* Part I).

Fraction V (b. p. 50-53°/1·5 mm.) showed a violet fluorescence alone or in ether solution. The picrate isolated from ether solution in the usual manner was obtained as a sticky precipitate which dissolved in alcohol leaving some dark impurities. From the orange-red solution the picrate crystallised on keeping, m. p. 128-30°. After repeated crystallisations from methyl alcohol it was obtained as woolly yellow prisms, m. p. 172° after softening at 163-168°. After drying at 100° in *vacuo* it lost 2·6% (loss of $\frac{1}{2}$ H₂O requires 2·3 per cent). It depressed the m. p. of the picrates of quinoline and isoquinoline and differed from them in other details also. [Found in anhydrous material: C, 52·3, 52·4; H, 3·9, 4·0; N, 13·8, 14·0. C₁₁H₁₁N·C₆H₂(NO₂)₃(OH) requires C, 52·8; H, 3·6; N, 14·5 per cent. C₁₁H₁₁N·C₆H₂(NO₂)₃(OH) requires C, 52·6; H, 4·1; N, 14·4 per cent].

The filtrates from all the above fractions yielded crystalline bright yellow picrates of varying melting points and were not investigated.

The micro-analyses were done by Dr. Weiller and Dr. Strauss, Oxford.

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